

THE WORLD IN SCHEMATICS

Volume 1

Sokhi Huda
Da'wa & Communication Faculty
Sunan Ampel State Islamic University
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FOREWORD

This volume 1 of the presentation slide is a collection of 24 schemes from 14 articles and conference papers. The author deliberately entitled this collection "The World in Schematics" to facilitate identification of the uniqueness of the idea. The argument that is built is that a scientific explanation of the world can be systematically simplified into a schematic form.

Each part begins with the work's identity and nice point. A nice point (NP) is a brief and reflective description of the results of a particular study or research. The language packaging is efficient and effective with the most important diction that the researcher wants to give. NP shows the richness of diction, the breadth of reading insight, mastery of research results, as well as the ability to reflect a writer. On this condition, NP is like a string of pearls in the integrity of the author's idea of a problem.

Surabaya, January 23, 2021

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PART 1

Scheme Code	: 2017.PPDS
Title	: Sufistic Da'wa Thought and Praxis of M. Fethullah Gülen
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Islamica: Jurnal Studi Keislaman</i>, Vol. 11 No. 2 (Maret 2017): 396-423, p-ISSN: 1978-3183, e-ISSN: 2356-2218
DOI	: 10.15642/islamica.2017.11.2.311-338
URL	: http://islamica.uinsby.ac.id/index.php/islamica/article/view/327/464
<i>Nice Point</i>	: Gülen's preaching thought developed and could be accepted by the global community. This thought exists to spread the ideas of love, tolerance and pluralism and has received a lot of attention from more than 160 countries. The praxis is manifested in the practice of da'wa with a methodical system that puts forward the hizmet movement with contemporary philanthropic tactics and media. The role of this praxis is to produce a progressive golden generation, contribute to enhancing the positive image of Islam and Muslims and the moral development of the world community. (Sokhi Huda, 1-03-2017)

Figure 2017.PPDS
Idealism Scheme of the Golden Generation
in the Version of the Gülen's Thought

IN SUNAN AMP
R.A.B.A

PART 2

Scheme Code	: 2018 ICSM
Title	: Moral Spirit in the Sufistic Da'wa of the Hizmet Movement of M. Fethullah Gülen
Source/ Publisher	: <i>International Joint Colloquium on Postgraduate Research Findings</i> (Surabaya: Pascasarjana UIN Sunan Ampel, 11-12 April 2018)
DOI	: 10.5281/zenodo.1216217
URL	: https://www.zenodo.org/record/1216217
<i>Nice Point</i>	: Hizmet is the most global transnational Islamic movement and emphasizes altruistic service. Hizmet became a da'wah movement with a Sufism approach, with the central character of M. Fethullah Gülen. The movement's inspirations include education, interfaith and intercultural dialogue, and social assistance and services. The moral spirit is "life is dedication". Hizmet has three factors as the key to success; (1) Sufism as the spirit of selfless service, (2) the efficacy of the movement's vision in the packaging of progressive new thinking, and (3) the ability to transform various sources into effective social capital. (Sokhi Huda, 12-04-2018)

INSPIRATIONAL CIRCLE WITH SONAR MODEL

Source: Sokhi Huda, 2017

PART 3

Scheme Code	:	2004.PID
Title	:	The Paradigm of Da'wa Science and Its Development through Empirical Studies
Source/ Publisher	:	<i>Jurnal Ilmu Dakwah</i> , Vol. 9 No. 1 (April 2004): 14-29. ISSN: 1411-4724x
DOI	:	10.5281/zenodo.1174500
URL	:	http://catalog.uinsby.ac.id//index.php?p=show_detail&id=44970
<i>Nice Point</i>	:	The Da'wa Science Paradigm (DSP) is a fundamental view of what is the subject matter of the science of da'wa. PID symbolizes the clarity of the vision of da'wa science. This vision is translated into a mission in the form of a study profile and its objectives which are translated into various study approaches. DSP can be developed through empirical studies with the pattern of "interpretative social sciences" which emphasizes ethnographic deepening. The goal and objective of this development is the discovery of new theories. The level of analysis used is grounded research analysis.

Figure 2004.PID
General System of the Paradigm of Da'wah Science

PART 4

Scheme Code	:	2008.MSKD
Title	:	Sketching the Concept of Contemporary Da'wa (Historical-Paradigmatic Perspective)
Source/ Publisher	:	<i>Al-'Adalah: Jurnal Kajian Keislaman dan Masyarakat</i> , Vol. 11 No. 2 (Agustus 2008): 253-272, ISSN: 1410-7406
DOI	:	10.5281/zenodo.1174480
URL	:	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321375722 .
<i>Nice Point</i>	:	Da'wa in the contemporary era cannot impose itself by using arrogant/radical models or prioritizing explanations, justification models, or even romantic models, speculatively. He is required to be able to combine all of these models into a new packaging that is more creative, decorative, basic, and non-responsive. This concoction is characteristic of contemporary da'wa. Da'i realize and treat mad'u fairly and affectionately as he treats himself. This awareness and treatment is the grand idea (spirit) of contemporary da'wa. This spirit is at the core of the contemporary da'wa concept sketch proposed in this paper.

Figure 2008.MSKD
Concept Scheme of the Contemporary Islamic Preaching

PART 5

Scheme Code	:	2014.KPM
Title	:	Criticism of Richard C. Martin's Thought in Religious Studies and Its Relevance to Islamic Studies in Indonesia
Source/ Publisher	:	<i>Religio: Jurnal Studi Agama-Agama</i> , Vol.4, No.1 (Maret 2014): 98-123, p-ISSN: 2088-6330, e-ISSN: 2503-3778,
DOI	:	10.5281/zenodo.1174149
URL	:	http://jurnalfuf.uinsby.ac.id/index.php/religio/article/view/505
<i>Nice Point</i>	:	If Richard C. Martin had been asked to talk about the conditions of Islamic studies in Indonesia, he might have said in Gus Dur's style: "That's all, it's a hassle! Here, I contributed five parts, seven approaches, and eleven data fields (formulas 5-7-11). If it's still lacking, I'll invite my good friend Charles J. Adams and others to contribute. However, don't forget the Phenomenology approach to solve insider and outsider problems. (Sokhi Huda, 01-11-2010)

Figure 2014.KPM
Bagan 1. Alur Pemikiran Richard C. Martin
Tentang Pendekatan terhadap Islam dalam Studi Agama

PART 6

Scheme Code	: 2011.TMI.1, 2011.TMI.2, 2011.TMI.3, 2011.TMI.4
Title	: Mustad'afin Theology in Indonesia: A Study on Muhammadiyah Theology
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Tsaqafah: Jurnal Peradaban Islam</i>, Vol. 7 No. 2 (Oktober 2011): 345-374, p-ISSN; 1411-0334, e-ISSN: 2460-0008
DOI	: 10.21111/tsaqafah.v7i2.8
URL	: http://ejournal.unida.gontor.ac.id/index.php/tsaqafah/article/view/8
Nice Point	: Mustad'afin's theology, as a new feature of al-Ma`un theology, is in the forefront of its turbulence with contemporary challenges; understanding of nationality, local traditions, cultural development, organizational economic factors, political dynamics, and modern and contemporary scientific criticism. His liberation project is demanded to get out of the hegemony of the exclusive Wahhabi-Salafi theology, so that he can be accepted significantly as a liberation movement in Indonesia. At this scale, the Nahdlatul Ulama's tradition, which was originally an easy target for the theology of al-Maun, has in turn taken its treasures into account and cooperated as partners in its practical strategy to solve a number of contemporary problems of the Indonesian nation and state. (Sokhi Huda, 11-07-2011)

Figure 2011.TMI.1
Chart of the Epistemology Pillars of Theology of *Mustad'afin*

Figure 2011.TMI.2
Chart of Dimensions, Spirits, and Characteristics
of Theology of *Mustad'afin*

Figure 2011.TMI.3
Chart of Acceptable Contemporary Theology

Figure 2011.TMI.4
Chart of Philosophical Construction of Theology of *Mustad'afin*

PART 7

Scheme Code	: 2012.PMM
Title	: Muhammadiyah's Modern Thought: From Historical Dialectics to Epistemological Problems
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Menara Tebuireng: Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Keislaman</i> , Vol. 8 No. 1 (September 2012): 1-18, ISSN: 1829-801X
DOI	: 10.5281/zenodo.1181844
URL	: http://isjd.pdii.lipi.go.id/index.php/Search.html?act=tampil&id=160100&idc=1
<i>Nice Point</i>	: In the age of one century, Muhammadiyah was tested by historical criticism in its ideological-theological settings, sociological realities, political affairs, and challenges of ijtihad in the thoughts of its future generations. The historical dialectic that it experienced left an epistemological problem that spawned thought and cultural dialogue initiatives. The emergence of self-criticism and inter-criticism of Muhammadiyah in the dynamics of the Islamic movement is a serious necessity. Its interpretation carries an "ideological mystery" which is realized in the constellation of his modern thought. (Sokhi Huda, 10-05-2011)

Figure 2012.PMM
One Century of the Muhammadiyah's Modern Thought

PART 8

Scheme Code	:	2002.NHFS
Title	:	Humanistic Values within Advocacy of al-Imam al-Shafi'i's Fiqh against Women
Source/ Publisher	:	<i>Antologi Kajian Islam</i> , Pascasarjana IAIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, Seri 2, Juni 2002, 145-156
DOI	:	10.5281/zenodo.1165351
URL	:	https://zenodo.org/record/1165352
Nice Point	:	God has no interest whatsoever in the shari'ah He makes. On the other hand, shari'ah is the legitimacy of human behavior according to its humanistic level. The advocacy of jurisprudence of al-Imam al-Shafi'i is carried out by honoring, enlivening functions, giving freedom, providing self-protection tools, fighting for rights, and elevating the dignity of women as human beings. The goal is for women to acquire their dynamics as a persona and reality, for the attainment of their existence, definition, and meaning in life that moves to serve. (Sokhi Huda, June 2002)

Figure 2002.NHFS
The Humanistic Values System in the fiqh of al-Imam al-Shafi'i

PART 9

Scheme Code	: 2013.KHPP
Title	: Controversy over the Rights and Role of Women within Contemporary Thought of Amina Wadud
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Urwatul Wutsqo: Jurnal Studi Kependidikan dan Keislaman</i> , Vol.2 No.2 (September 2013): 87-112, ISSN: 2252-6099
DOI	: 10.5281/zenodo.1174230
URL	: http://ejournal.kopertais4.or.id/mataraman/index.php/wutsqa/article/view/1000
<i>Nice Point</i>	: Amina Wadud is a contemporary thinker who displays a bold and courageous figure, as well as a high level of controversy. She has broken down the walls of the conventional paradigm that had been solidly defended over the previous 14 centuries. This breakthrough was carried out by Wadud not only in the conceptual realm but also in the realm of praxis. Its main project is the struggle for gender justice in the context of the universal values of the Koran regarding justice, dignity, equality of rights, responsibility, and human social equilibrium. (Sokhi Huda, 07-07-2011)

Figure 2013.KHPP
Wadud's Hermeneutics of the Qur'an on the Controversy
on the Rights and Roles of Women

PART 10

Scheme Code	:	2011.IMHI.1, 2011.IMHI.2, 2011.IMHI.3, 2011.IMHI.4
Title	:	Methodological Innovations in the Constellation of Islamic Law
Source/ Publisher	:	Wasid dkk, <i>Menafsirkan Tradisi dan Modernitas: Ide-Ide Pembaharuan Islam</i> (Surabaya: Pustaka Idea, Juli 2011), 43-65, ISBN: 602-993-8711, ISBN 13: 978-602-99387-1-5
DOI	:	10.5281/zenodo.1181854
URL	:	https://zenodo.org/record/1181854
<i>Nice Point</i>	:	Muhammad Shahrur's works speak for themselves, that he is a thinker who dares to oppose the flow of conventions, deconstructs, and at the same time offers new recipes based on philosophical views, historical reconstructive approaches, and hermeneutic methods so as to produce methodological innovations in Islamic law, even though he has never been called an expert. tafsir and fiqh. The temperature of the controversy rose when Shahrur was found to have a self-taught background, a professor of Civil Engineering, and the son of a dye in the Arab region. (Sokhi Huda, 01-11-2010)

Figure 2011.IMHL.1
The Construction Scheme of Muhammad Shahrur's Thought

Figure 2011.IMHI.2
The Construction Diagram of
Muhammad Shahrur's Thought

Figure 2011.IMHL.3

Tabel 1. Muhammad Shahrur's Methodological Innovation of Islamic Law in Comparing the Spirit of Conventional Islamic Law Theories

No.	Notable	Territory Origin and Lifespan	Legal Theory	Accentuation of Legal Spirit	Developmental Constellation
1	Malik bin Anas	93-179 H/713-795 M, born in Madinah	<i>Maṣlaḥah Mursalah</i>	Benefit persuasive and anticipation of danger	The persuasive and anticipatory nature of Islamic law
2	Abu Hanifah	81-150 M/700-767 H, born in Kufah, wafat di Baghdad	<i>Istihṣān</i>	For whose good, not what, namely society	The mercy nature of Islamic law
3	Al-Shafi'i	150-206 H/767-820 M, born in Gaza, Palestina	<i>Qiyās</i>	The reasons/considerations in establishing law, based on research	Raising research in Islamic law <i>(ijtihad)</i> (development)
4	Ibnu Hanbal	l. 164 H/780 M, in Baghdad	<i>Istishāb</i>	Practical, simple, and cultural principles	Practical way of applying Islamic law
5	Al-Ghazali	405-505 H/ 1058-1111 M	<i>Intermediate/ Alternative</i>	Adding an element of benefit in <i>istihṣān</i>	Solutive nature of Islamic law
6	Al-Shaṭibi	730 H-790 H/1388 M, born in Granada	<i>Maqāṣid al-Sharī'ah</i>	The contextuality of the meaning of <i>Shari'</i> and the meaning of <i>mukallaḥ</i>	The contextual nature of Islamic law
7	Shahrur	Born 1938 in Damaskus, Suriah	<i>Hudūd (Limit)</i>	Applicability dynamics and action control	The dynamic and elastic nature of Islamic law

Figure 2011.IMHI.4
The Methodological Innovation Scheme of Muḥammad Shaḥrūr
in the Constellation of Islamic Law

PART 11

Scheme Code	: 2012.BFI.1, 2012.BFI.2
Title	: West and Islamic Fundamentalism: The Battle between Existence and Ambition
Source/ Publisher	: Jurnal Reflektika IDIA Prenduan, Vol.5 (Muharram 1434 H/Nopember 2012 M): 15-47, p-ISSN: 2337-6821; e-ISSN: 2580-4006
DOI	: 10.5281/zenodo.1174279
URL	: http://digilib.uinsby.ac.id/id/eprint/17965
<i>Nice Point</i>	: West and Islam hold the status of key actors in the history of global civilization. The inter-contributive relationship between the two, with the remaining agenda of prejudice, has shifted to a pattern of increasingly demanding interegoist relationships. Its current was stabilized by the tragedy of 9/11, a product of the action of Islamic fundamentalism. As a measure of resistance and survival, the West has produced a number of policies (political, economic, and military) that have actually encouraged the growth of Islamic fundamentalism. The competition for a superior position makes clear the face of the ambition to strengthen existence and the struggle for identity. At its peak, interegoist relations formed the dialectic of Western and Islamic existence, ambition, and identity. (Sokhi Huda, 13-06-2011)

Figure 2012.BFI.1
Profile of Relations between the West and Islamic Fundamentalism

Figure 2012.BFI.2
The Battle of Existence and Ambition between the West and Islamic Fundamentalism

PART 12

Scheme Code	: 2011.GS.1, 2011.GS.2
Title	: Global Salafism: A New Perspective on the Uniqueness of Islamic Radicalism
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Kontemplasi: Jurnal Ilmu Ke-Ushuluddin</i> , Vol. 8, No. 2 (Nopember 2011: 213-228, ISSN: 0216-6399)
DOI	: 10.5281/zenodo.1175597
URL	: http://digilib.uinsby.ac.id/id/eprint/18591
<i>Nice Point</i>	: In fact, emotional tension cannot be stopped because of the pressure of historical criticism experienced by Muslims. Part of the phenomenal-global result is self-imposed to proclaim Islam as the best value, strength, and power that must be recognized by the world. This fact has provoked the emergence of a new perspective on the uniqueness of Islamic radicalism, whose terms refer to the unique Islamic vocabulary; Hanbalism, Wahhabism, Salafism, Islamist, Jihadism, and other related terms. On a critical scale, the global nature of Islam's mercy is turning into a global threat; violence, terrorism, and intolerance. (Sokhi Huda, 10-01-2011)

Figure 2011.GS
Scheme and Triangle of the Global Salafism

Figure 1. Global Salafism Scheme

Figure 2. Global Salafism Triangle

Historical Reality of Salafism:

- Emotional tension (psychophobia) over historical criticism;
- The nature of global grace of Islam turns into a global threat.

Constructive attitude as a need (therapy):

- ✓ Introspection and self-revitalization as a control;
- ✓ Relationship dialog as rapprochement.

PART 13

Scheme Code	: 2014.TKDI
Title	: Contemporary Terrorism of the Islamic World
Source/ Publisher	: <i>Teosofi: Jurnal Tasawuf dan Pemikiran Islam</i>, Vol.4 No.2 (Desember 2014): 429-450, ISSN: 2088-7957, e-ISSN: 2442-871X
DOI	: 10.15642/teosofi.2014.4.2.429-450
URL	: http://teosofi.uinsby.ac.id/index.php/teosofi/article/view/17/15
<i>Nice Point</i>	: Terrorism, as part of historical integrity, plays a control role over tyranny-domination and the role of ideological actualization. Armed with an institutionalized historical legacy, he does not only express for a moment but penetrates the skates of the historical period, and with an emphasis on problem-solving in the contemporary era, acts of terrorism are required to provide a timely response. All worldly risks are completely immersed in the meaning of faith which is full of substance. (Sokhi Huda, 20-06-2011)

Figure 2014.TKDI
The Unique Figure of Terrorism within the Contemporary Islamic Discourse

PART 14

Scheme Code	: 2018 SPGIK
Title	: Structure of Contemporary Islamic Thought and Movements
Source/ Publisher	: Al-Tahrir: Jurnal Pemikiran Islam, Vol. 18 No. 1 (Mei 2018): Islam: Liberalism & Fundamentalism: 155-178, p-ISSN: 1412- 7512, e-ISSN: 2502-2210
DOI	: 10.21154/altahrir.v18i1.1199
URL	: http://jurnal.stainponorogo.ac.id/index.php/tahrir/article/view/1199
<i>Nice Point</i>	: The variations of thought and progressive movements in the Islamic world provide solutions to a number of contemporary problems. This variation shows its distinctive character and can be shaped into a general structure pattern consisting of 5 aspects and 14 components. All these aspects and components move in a hierarchical and circular manner. Hierarchical motion shows the vertical-interactive relation from the highest level to the lowest level. The circular motion shows a referential relation from the lowest level which tries to trace its source to the highest level for the fulfillment of progressive solutions with reinterpreted and historical approaches. (Sokhi Huda, 01-05-2018)

Figure: The Pyramid of the Structure of Thoughts and Movements of the Contemporary Islam

Source: Sokhi Huda, 2018

